

STRATEGY FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT

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Introduction

Development cooperation Focusing on rural development is a very important component. Industrial development and adoptions of modern technology are likely to generate additional employment in urban areas and pay rich divined to elite and rich investors. Fortunately, the India has been giving top priority to rural development. However, in the absence of well planned development programmes most of these resources do not benefit the target groups. Poor families have received sympathy instead of motivation which has resulted in the dependency syndrome.

The time is how rip for a change in the strategy. The rural development programme should indentify the rural development programme should identify the problems of the poor and address the local needs. The participating families should take active part in the programme. The programme should facilitate sustainable development.

Definition of Rural Development:

The use of rural as a relative concept to urban based on social, economical, and natural conditions in each country may be most adequate.

Most rural residents in many developing countries are engaged in the developed on local agriculture, forestry and fishery resources to make a living.

According to the world Banti (1975), rural development is defined as a strategy aiming at the improvement of economic and social living conditions, focusing on a specific group of poor people in a rural area. It assists the poorest group among the people living in rural areas to benefit from development.

Need for rural Development:

- For the important at Indian economy
- To improve profits for farmers
- To reduce urbanization
- To produce variety of food products agriculture.

Effective ruler Development strategies:

• Development of project proposals

Based on the local needs and available opportunities, it is preferable to prepare a project proposal for raising financial resources. The proposal should cover various aspects such as infrastructures

needs, identification of the target groups and the activities to be taken. The community should be involved in project implementation right from the beginning.

• **Provision of technology inputs:**

The development inputs in general consists of technology and resources. As there is no constraint in acquiring technology from various sources, it is neither feasible nor necessary to restrict the dissemination of technology.

• **By adopting localized way of distributing agricultural products:**

Marketing is a dynamic process which is influenced by demand and supply as well as information on new products. For the success of any rural development programme, there is a need for a strong local organization having a strong linkage with technology centers.

• **Water management for agricultural production:**

Water is the lifeline of all human activities water is not only needed for survival but also for generating employment in rural areas. The selection of villages for development can cover the entire area under a watershed with the development of water resources, various income generation activities can be initiated.

Conclusion:

Most of the rural people depend on agriculture so there is a great need to follow the effective rural development strategies for improving the quality of rural areas.

References:

- Chambers,R.(1983). *Rural Development*, Longman Scientific.
- Moraka,M. (2000). *Decentralisation and participant sustainable rural Development*, University of Africa.
- Gray,R. (1991). *Economic Measure of susta*: Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economic Vol.